

Determination of the Critical Micelle Concentration and Study of the Physical Properties of the System : Barium Valerate-Water and Propanol-1

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The critical micelle concentration of barium valerate has been determined by studying the density, viscosity, surface tension and conductivity of the soap solutions in mixtures of water and propanol-1. Szyszkowski's equation has been applied to calculate the surface area covered by one g. mole of the soap and to find out the size and the nature of the micelles formed in soap solutions. The results confirm that the change in the nature of the micelles takes place at about 50% propanol-1 concentration.

In the previous communications¹⁻³, the molecular conductivity, surface tension and molar refraction of the system : barium soap-water and propanol-1 have been investigated. In the present work, the properties (viz., solubility, density, viscosity, surface tension and molecular conductivity of barium valerate solutions in water-propanol-1 mixtures of varying compositions have been studied. The work has been initiated with a view to find out the C.M.C. and to investigate the nature of the micelles formed in soap solutions under different conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of soap solutions : Merck reagent grade propanol-1 and *n*-valeric acid were used and purified by distilling under reduced pressure. Purity of the reagents was confirmed by the determination of their boiling points.

Sodium valerate was prepared by refluxing equivalent amounts of *n*-valeric acid and sodium hydroxide for 10-12 hrs. on a water bath. The soap was purified by recrystallization from alcohol and then dried in vacuum.

Barium valerate was prepared by direct metathesis of the sodium soap with the required amount of barium hydroxide at 50-55°. The precipitated barium soap was washed with water and then with alcohol to remove the free precipitant and acid, respectively. After initial drying in an air oven at 100-105°, the final drying was carried out under reduced pressure.

A calculated amount of the soap was weighed in a standard flask and the solution was produced by adding required amounts of propanol-1 and conductivity water. In this way a number of solutions of 0-90% propanol-1 containing different soap concentrations were prepared.

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1. K. N. Mehrotra and R. P. Varma, *J. Amer. Oil Chemists' Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 673.
2. K. N. Mehrotra and R. P. Varma, *J. Amer. Oil Chemists' Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 152.
3. K. N. Mehrotra and R. P. Varma, *Kolloid-Z.*, 1969, **233**, 934.

No attempt was made to determine the exact solubilities of the soap but an idea was obtained by finding the range (within 0.0125*M*) above which the solutions of higher concentration could not be prepared.

All measurements were made in a thermostat at constant temperature ($40 \pm 0.05^\circ$). A Kohlrausch Universal Bridge (W. G. Pye and Co. Ltd., Cambridge, England) and a dipping type conductivity cell with the platinized electrodes were used for measuring the conductance of the soap solutions. The density, viscosity and surface tension of the soap solutions were measured by means of pycnometer, Ostwald's viscometer and stalagmometer, respectively. The reproducibility of the measurements was examined by repeating the measurements several times.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Solubility: The solubility of barium valerate in water-propanol-1 mixtures at first increases (upto 30% propanol-1) and then decreases with the increase in propanol-1 concentration (Table I). This difference may be due to the change in the nature of the solvent which occurs with the variation in the solvent composition.

TABLE I

Temperature $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$

Volume % of Propanol-1	Solubility in g.moles/ litre	Density		Viscosity in millipoise	
		Extrapo- lated	Experi- mental	Extrapo- lated	Experi- mental
0	0.345	0.999	0.9930	6.6	6.56
10	0.425	0.987	0.9840	11.3	11.32
20	0.505	0.973	0.9696	12.9	12.55
30	0.665	0.956	0.9532	14.4	14.21
40	0.545	0.935	0.9340	15.4	15.34
50	0.425	0.915	0.9133	16.7	16.81
60	0.385	0.894	0.8925	17.2	17.18
70	0.305	0.872	0.8708	17.4	17.30
80	0.185	0.852	0.8463	16.9	16.35
90	0.065	0.826	0.8270	15.8	15.42

Density: The density of valerate solutions in mixtures of water-propanol-1 increases with the increase in the soap concentration. The plots of density, ρ , against soap concentration (g.moles/litre), C , are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a definite soap concentration which is independent of the solvent composition (Fig. 1). This definite concentration corresponds to critical micelle concentration, C.M.C. at which there is a sudden change in the aggregation of the soap molecules. The C.M.C. for valerate is 0.025 *M* and is in agreement with the value obtained from the studies of refractive indices of soap solutions³.

The plots of density against soap concentration are extrapolated to zero soap concentration and the extrapolated values for different compositions of the solvent (water and

FIG. 1.
DENSITY AGAINST SOAP CONCENTRATION

propanol-1) mixture are summarised in Table I. It is observed that the extrapolated values of density, ρ_0 , are in agreement with the densities of the solvent mixture. It is, therefore, concluded that the soap molecules do not show appreciable aggregation below C.M.C. whereas at this definite soap concentration there is a marked change in the aggregation of the soap molecules.

The densities of valerate solutions as well as of the solvent mixture at first decrease non-linearly (upto 50% propanol-1) and then linearly with the increase in propanol-1 concentration (Fig. 2). This may be due to the change in the nature of the solvent which occurs as the amounts of water and propanol-1 are varied in the system. A change in behaviour at 50% propanol-1 concentration is also observed in molar refraction studies³.

Viscosity: The viscosity of the soap solutions increases with the increase in soap concentration and this may be due to the increasing tendency to form aggregates with the increase in soap concentration. The viscosities of the soap solutions at first increase linearly

(upto 0.025 *M* soap concentration) and then non-linearly with the increase in soap concentration. The linear portion of the plots of viscosity, η , against soap concentration, C , are extrapolated to zero soap concentration and it is found that the extrapolated values of viscosity, η_0 , are in close agreement with the viscosity of the solvent (water propanol-1) mixture (Table I). This confirms that the soap molecules do not show appreciable aggregation below C.M.C. and there is a sudden change in the aggregation at C.M.C.

The plots of fluidity, $[\phi = 1/\eta]$, against reciprocal of density, $1/\rho$, show a change at a definite point corresponding to 0.025 *M* soap concentration for all compositions of water and propanol-1 mixture (Fig. 3). The variation of fluidity, ϕ , with reciprocal of density, $1/\rho$, is characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at C.M.C., (0.025 *M*), and it is found that the values of C.M.C. are independent of the solvent composition.

The viscosity of the soap solutions at first increases linearly as the volume percent of propanol-1 increases to 50%, then slowly (between 50 to 70% propanol-1) and finally decreases with the increase in propanol-1 concentration (Fig. 4). This difference may be due

to the change in the nature of the soap micelles which takes place at about 50% propanol-1 concentration. The increase in viscosity below 70% propanol-1 concentration may be due to the increase in the size of the micelles as the alcohol is also incorporated in the micelles. The decrease in viscosity above 70% propanol-1 concentration may be due to the decrease in the degree of aggregation with the increase in propanol-1 concentration.

Surface tension : The surface tension of the system barium valerate water and propanol-1 decreases with the increase in the soap concentration and the decrease may be due to the increasing tendency to form aggregates with the increase in soap concentration. The plots of surface tension, γ , against the soap concentration, C , show a sharp change in the surface deficiency of the soap at a definite soap concentration 0.025 M , for all the compositions of solvent (water-propanol-1) mixture. This definite concentration corresponds to C.M.C. and is found to be independent of the composition of the solvent mixture.

The surface tension of valerate solutions decreases with the increase in volume percent of propanol-1 which may be due to the increasing size of the micelles as the alcohol is also incorporated in the soap micelles. The surface tension of the soap solutions at first decreases rapidly, then slowly and finally linearly with the increase in propanol-1 concentration. The plots of surface tension, γ , against volume percent of propanol-1 exhibit a change at 50% propanol-1 concentration (Fig. 5) which may be due to the change in the nature of the micelles

FIG. 4.
 VISCOSITY, η , AGAINST VOLUME PERCENT OF PROPANOL I

formed in soap solutions. A change at 50% propanol-1 concentration has also been observed in density and viscosity results.

Surface area : The plots (Fig. 6) of surface tension, γ , against logarithm of soap concentration, $\log C$, are linear for solutions containing 20% to 90% propanol-1 whereas the

plot for 10% propanol-1 exhibits deviation from the linear behaviour at high soap concentrations ($> 0.045 M$). Similar behaviour has also been observed in our previous communication². The results for 20% to 90% propanol-1 systems are in agreement with the Szyszkowski's⁴ empirical equation for solutions of fatty acids :

$$\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_0} = 1 - X \ln \frac{C}{Y}$$

where γ and γ_0 are the surface tension of the solution of soap concentration (g.moles/litre), C , and of the pure solvent, respectively and X and Y are constants.

On comparing the differential form of this equation with Gibbs adsorption equation, we get

$$\tau = - \frac{1}{RT} \frac{d\gamma}{d \ln C} = \frac{X\gamma_0}{RT}$$

where τ is the concentration of the solute per unit area of the surface.

Hence, the surface area, 'A', covered by the soap micelles formed by 1 g.mole of the soap :

$$A = \frac{RT}{X\gamma_0}$$

The values of X , Y and A have been calculated and are summarised in Table II. It is observed that the values of X , ($= 0.005$), calculated from the slopes of the plots of γ against $\log C$, are independent of the composition of the solvent mixture and so the area

TABLE II
Values of X , Y , $-X \ln Y$ and A

Volume % of Propanol-1	X	Y	$(-X \ln Y)$	$A \times 10^{-10}$ in cm^2
10	0.007	3.1×10^{-5}	0.07	14.54
20	0.005	2.6×10^{-7}	0.07	18.56
30	0.005	5.6×10^{-5}	0.05	20.24
40	0.005	3.4×10^{-5}	0.06	20.78
50	0.005	6.1×10^{-2}	0.01	21.96
60	0.005	1.8×10^{-2}	0.02	22.18
70	0.005	4.0×10^{-3}	0.03	22.48
80	0.005	6.8×10^{-2}	0.01	23.11
90	0.005	5.7×10^{-2}	0.01	23.48

covered by the soap micelles formed by 1 g.mole of the soap depends only on the surface tension of the solvent mixture. The surface tension of water-propanol-1 mixtures decreases with the increase in propanol-1 concentration and hence results in the increase in the surface area covered by the soap micelle and which may be due to the fact that alcohol is also incorporated in the micelle. The value of X , ($= 0.007$), calculated from the linear portion of the plot for 10% propanol-1 is higher than that for 20% to 90% propanol-1 system and so 1 g.mole of the soap covers less surface area in presence of 10% propanol-1. This is in agreement with the view that the size of the micelles increases as the volume percent of propanol-1 in the system increases.

It may be pointed out that the values of Y , calculated from the intercepts, [$= \gamma_0 (1 + X \ln Y)$], of the plots of γ against $\log C$, for soap solutions containing 50% to 90% propanol-1 are much higher than that of the solutions containing propanol-1 below 50% (Table II). This difference may be due to the fact that Y depends on the nature of the micelles formed in soap solutions in mixed solvents. The large difference in the values of Y (below and above 50% propanol-1) suggests that the change in the nature of the micelles occurs at about 50% propanol-1 concentration.

The results show that X is independent of the solvent composition whereas the values of Y show a marked change at 50% propanol-1 concentration. It may also be pointed out that the values of $(-X \ln Y)$ for systems containing propanol-1 below 50% are much higher than that for the systems containing propanol-1 above 50% (Table II). This again confirms that the change in the nature of the micelles takes place at about 50% propanol-1 concentration.

The surface area covered by 1 g.mole of the barium valerate is $(18-23) \times 10^{10}$ cm².

Therefore, there is justification in applying the Szyszkowski's equation to find the the size and nature of the micelles formed in soap solutions in water-propanol-1 mixtures of varying compositions. The values of X and Y are suggestive of the size and nature of the micelles, respectively.

Molecular conductivity : The molecular conductivity of barium valerate solutions in water-propanol-1 mixtures of varying compositions decreases as the volume percent of propanol-1 in the system increases. The decrease in conductivity may be due to the combined effects of the variation of dielectric constant, hydration, degree of aggregation and viscosity with the change in the solvent composition. The plots of molecular conductivity, μ , against volume percent of propanol-1 show a break at 50% propanol-1 concentration (Fig. 7) which

Fig. 7.
MOLECULAR CONDUCTIVITY, μ , AGAINST VOLUME PERCENT
OF
PROPANOL-1

may be due to the fact that the change in the nature of the micelles occurs at about 50% propanol-1 concentration. A change in behaviour at 50% propanol-1 concentration has also been observed in density, viscosity and surface tension studies.

It is also observed that the molecular conductivity of the soap solutions decreases with the increase in soap concentration. The decrease is due to the increasing tendency to form aggregates with the increase in the soap concentration. The plots of molecular conductivity, μ , against square root of soap concentration, $C^{1/2}$, are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a point corresponding to C.M.C. (Fig. 8). It may be pointed out that the C.M.C. is independent of the solvent composition and the value obtained from conductivity measurements is in agreement with the C.M.C. obtained from density, viscosity and surface tension studies.

Fig. 8.

MOLECULAR CONDUCTIVITY, μ , AGAINST $C^{1/2}$

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